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Subsurface Investigation on Federal Route Failure at Pengkalan Raja, Pontian, Johor

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Abstract. Road settlement is one of the major problems that often occurs in soft soil ground areas. The combination of destructive test method (trial pit, Standard Penetration Test (SPT) and borehole) and non-destructive method by using seismic refraction, electrical resistivity tomography (ERT) and ground penetrating radar (GPR) were performed to identify the factor causing the tension cracks and road differential settlement. The study area selected is at Section 39 to 50, Federal Route (FT005) Johor Bahru to Malacca (Pengkalan Raja, Pontian, Johor) because of the severe road condition which may cause an accident to road user. This paper presenting the result of destructive and a non-destructive test. From results of borehole, seismic, and ERT, the road was underlaid by 7-12m of a soft compressible layer. The GPR image showed the existing of concrete slab below the road has deviated from its original position and may not function as a foundation of road. In conclusion, the combination of destructive and non-destructive method is best approach in identifying the underground failure because it is the fastest solution, economical and suitable in area of high volume of traffic.

Keywords: Differential settlement; Geotechnical forensic investigation; Destructive method; and Geophysical survey.

1. Introduction

Road settlement is one of failure mechanism occurred typically because of excessive loading caused the consolidation of soil beneath the structure moves either horizontally or vertically. The road settlement problem after post-construction has always been a challenge for designers and contractors to find the suitable treatment method especially in soft ground area. There are various techniques of geotechnical investigation such as destructive method and non-destructive method. Combination of destructive and non-destructive method of investigation are best assessment to understand the characteristic of underground soil and specific site condition. However, the selection of soil investigation methods that need to be adopted are dependent on the budget and the purposes of study.

Federal route (FT005) Johor Bahru–Malacca is the primary route connecting local resident travel to Johor Bahru and Singapore. Longitudinal tension crack and differential settlement were identified and repeated over than 10 years. This problem becomes a matter of concern for local authorities in Pontian, Johor. Due to limited cost of rehabilitation, surface treatment has been conducted to reduce

the risk of accident and minimise the severity of road failure. But that treatment was only effective to sustain for a short time period. Therefore, on year 2019, detail subsurface investigation was conducted to identify the factors causing the repeated failure. Thus, the result from detail investigation can be used by JKR District to propose the best method of treatment can be implemented. The subsurface investigation involved the destructive and non-destructive methods. The destructive methods that have been implemented in this study include Borehole, Standard Penetration Test (SPT) and trial pit. The non-destructive method, which is geophysical survey tests involved in this study, are 2-dimensional electrical resistivity (ERT), seismic survey and ground penetration radar (GPR). Geophysical survey test is an exploration method to determine the subsurface characteristic by measuring the physical properties of earth material [1]. Usually, the result from geophysical survey test shall verify with borehole's or standard penetration test's result. The geophysical survey test was selected because it is a faster method, can investigate large area, enhance interpretation and unseen subsurface [1]. Therefore, this paper is presented the result of testing involved both techniques (destructive and non-destructive) to determine the cause of road failure in the critical section along the road.

2. Study Area and General Geology

The sign of failure such as longitudinal cracking and differential settlement were identified along the Section 39 until Section 51, Federal Route Johor Bahru – Malacca (FT005) in Pengkalan Raja, Pontian. Two sites were selected as a study area, which is in Section 43.7 and Section 44 (Figure 1). The settlement identified along the slow lane and middle lane off the road. The pattern of road failure shown in Figure 2. According to the geological map (Figure 3), the study area was on marine deposited comprises clay, silt, sand and peat.

Figure 1. Location of study area along Section 39 to 51, Federal Road FT005.

Figure 2. The pattern of road failure at (a) Section 44 to 45 and (b) Section 42.

Figure 3. The geological map at study area.

3. Methodology of Study

The study has been performed in year 2019 was divided into three (3) phases of study comprise desk study, subsurface investigation and data analysis from the test's result. Desk study was conducted by collecting the in situ data via existing data or report, geology and topographical map included visual inspection along the distressed area for early prediction about site conditions along distress area. The subsurface investigation involved in this study was listed in the Table 1.

Table 1. List of geotechnical and geophysical test conducted in this study.

Method	Type of test	Location (Section)	Quantity	Remark
Destructive	Trial pit	40, 42 and 43.7	3 nos.	
	Borehole/ Standard Penetration Test (SPT) and laboratory testing*	43.7 and 44	2 nos.	BH1 and BH2
Non-destructive	2-dimensional electrical resistivity tomography (ERT)	43.7 and 44	7 lines	R1, R2, R3, R4, R5, R6 and R6a
	Seismic refraction	43.7 and 44	6 lines	S1, S2, S3, S4, S5, S6
	Ground penetration radar (GPR)	43.7 and 44	1.6km (grid line)	G1, G2, G3 and G4

Trial pit is a shallow investigation was conducted at the early stage of study to verify the strata profile of pavement layer and subsurface soil condition at the selected location along the failure section. The trenches were excavated by using an excavator or wheel backhoe with the depth was about one to two meters [2]. Data from the trial pit can be used as an early prediction about in situ problem and as a reference in identifying the quantity and type of test shall be performed. Borehole and Standard penetration test (SPT) were conducted at two (2) selected location along the failure section accordance to MS1056: Part 9 - Clause 5.4. The penetration resistance was determined by driven down split-barrel sampler using a 63.5kg hammer driven down into the ground. The disturbed samples were collected at 1.5m interval or change of strata for soil identification. Beside trial pit, borelog and SPT, a geophysical survey has been selected to compliment and verify with destructive test result. Geophysical survey is an exploration method to determine the subsurface characteristic by

measuring the physical properties of earth material [1]. This paper is present the finding from soil investigation's data that has been conducted which are borelog, SPT N-Value, 2D resistivity and seismic refraction survey and GPR. The result of ERT and seismic refraction survey were correlate to borehole and SPT in identifying the subsurface characteristic along the survey line.[3]

The seven (7) lines of ERT gradient protocol survey was conducted by using ABEM Terrameter LS2 to measure subsurface profile. The RES2DINV program is software used to process and convert the raw data into resistivity value (ohm.m). The typical resistivity value for a typical rock, soil material and water listed in Table 2 was used to interpret the underground material. Meanwhile, six (6) lines of seismic refraction were carried out in this study with 100m length per lines. The ABEM Terraloc MK-6 seismograph is an equipment to record the surface wave detected by 24 channels of vertical geophones at 2.5m spacing. The raw data of seismic refraction was processed with Optim Software to generate the subsurface soil profile. Beside to determine the subsurface profile, ground penetration radar (GPR) was carried out per route area along 100m length in both study areas to determine the current condition of the existing concrete slab beneath the pavement layer. GPR is the electromagnetic pulse reflection method performed using Noggin smart cart 250MHz system to detect anomalies or object below the pavement layer by using a high resolution of subsurface imaging called radargram [1]. The figure 4 shows the sketch of testing area at Section 43.7 and Section 44, FT005 Pengkalan Raja, Pontian, Johor.

Table 2. Resistivity of some common rock and soil materials [4].

Material	Resistivity (ohm.m)	Material	Resistivity (ohm.m)
Alluvium	10 to 800	Sand	60 to 1000
Clay	1 to 100	Groundwater (fresh)	10 to 100
Sandstone	8 to 4×10^3	Shale	20 to 2×10^3
Limestone	50 to 4×10^3	Granite	5000 to 1,000,000

Figure 4. The illustration of borehole, GPR grid line, ERT and Seismic survey lines.

4. Result and Discussion

4.1 Desk study – Existing report

Selia Selenggara Selatan Sdn. Bhd. (SSSSB) had produced a report on structural condition assessment along Section 38 until Section 45, FT005 on March 2019. The assessment was based on the results of falling weight deflectometer (FWD), coring and dynamic cone penetrometer (DCP). Based on the results of FWD listed in Table 3, the condition of the existing concrete slab is poor and the condition of a subgrade layer in the range is satisfactory to poor.

Table 3. The results of FWD along Section 38-45, FT005 [5].

FWD	Toward Malacca		Toward Johor Bahru	
	Without concrete slab	With concrete slab	Without concrete slab	With concrete slab
Asphalt Layer	Poor (75%)	Satisfactory (50%)	Poor (60%)	Satisfactory (100%)
Granular Layer	Satisfactory-Poor (50%)	Poor (75%)	Satisfactory (80%)	n.a.
Concrete Slab	n.a.	Poor (75%)	n.a.	Poor (66.7%)
Subgrade Layer	Poor (75%)	Satisfactory (100%)	Satisfactory (100%)	Satisfactory (100%)

The coring and DCP Test were done at three points located near to centre line of middle lane between Section 38-45, FT005. The results show the thickness of the asphaltic layer (bound layer) are between 177-282 mm where the unbound layer (crusher run) is between 255-478mm. The CBR value of Core 1 and Core 3 were difficult to determine due to the existence of concrete layer underneath the crusher run. The CBR value at point Core 2 is 9.97%. [4]. The typical thickness of asphalt layer usually applied for federal road around 110mm. The premix layer has been increased due to the settlement and repeated process of resurfacing. Besides that, based on visual inspection at the site, the road at elevated area was tendency to settle more compared with a non-elevated road. There was an instability problem that cause the tension crack and settlement at elevated road.

4.2 Subsurface investigation – Trial Pit

Trial pit has been carried out at section 40, 42 and 43.7 along FT005. There was proven that the road was built on a concrete slab. Based on trial pit, the thickness of the concrete slab found in the range 200-300mm seated on the subgrade layer (Figure 5). The width of slab is about 6m whereas the width of the road, including shoulder, is about 10m. The flexible pavement design with a different method of ground treatment was constructed at widening or slow lane area in both directions of route. Based on in situ observation, the longitudinal crack and settlement occurred at edge of the concrete slab. Meanwhile, the existing gap between two slabs below the pavement layers was the causal factor of cracking and deformation on the surface layer at the intermittent line. In addition, the repeated process of resurfacing (overlay or regulate) for a long time was thicken the asphalt layer in range 600 - 900mm.

Figure 5. (a) Road settlement at joint between the slab and ground at the slow lane (Section 42, FT005); and (b) The distance between two slabs was about 0.5m found at the middle line of road Section 43.7, FT005.

4.3 Subsurface Profile

Subsurface profile or soil strata along 100m length was identified from ERT and seismic. The confirmation of soil layer was determined from a borehole or SPT. The result of testing named as S1, R, BH1 and S5, R5 and BH2 were selected to represent the soil profile at were at Section 43.7 and 44, FT005. In this study, seismic refraction survey lines were conducted parallel to the alignment of road and overlap with ERT lines. The classification system applied for seismic refraction testing and ERT were referred to Table 4 and Table 5.

Table 4. The classification system on seismic refraction for soft clay.

Description of Material	P-wave Velocity, (Vp)	N-Values	Assesment	color
Cohesive soil (CLAY)	<900	0-2	Very soft	Dark Blue
	900-1000	2-4	Soft	Blue
	1000-1200	4-8	Medium stiff	Greenish Blue
	1200-1800	8-15	Stiff	Light Green
	1500-1800	15-30	Very stiff	Yellow Green
	>1800	>30	Hard	Yellow

Table 5. The classification for soft soil based on ERT value.

Resistivity Value (Ωm)	Legends	Interpretation
1 – 100	0.00, 5.00, 30.0, 60.0, 100	Zone of soil saturated with water
> 100	300, 500, 1000, 4000	Zone of unsaturated soil

The seismic refraction results (S1 and S5) were presented in the Figure 6. The value of P-wave velocity was recorded less than 900m/sec and detected at depth 9m from the ground surface, which is classified as cohesive soil. Compare with SPT N-values, there are no recorded numbers of blow (N-value = 0) from 1.5m to 9m depth and the log's data classified the layer as a very soil clay. The value of P-wave was increased as a depth increased. The result of seismic was compared to borehole result and SPT as shown in Figure 6. Figure 7 show the detail of soil strata profile plotted from the result of BH1 and BH2. There are presented 7m of soft clay layer underlain by 12m of very soft to firm clayey sandy silt. There was found that the organic matter is about 20% and can be concluded that the failure was not caused by the peat problem.

Line R5 and R1 were selected to represent the result of ERT at Section 43.7 and Section 44. The ERT was measured along 100m length as shown in Figure 8. Soil strata 3m below the road level was dominant with a low value of resistivity, which is less than 100 ohm.m and less 3 msec. Correlate to log's data, the layer consists of soft to stiff clay underlain the asphalt layer between 1.5m to 9.0m. Meanwhile, there are a potential zone of medium stiff to stiff clay layer with water saturated at depth 9.0m to 10.5m and followed by very stiff layer of sand or clay saturated with water. From result of boreholes, the ground water level was detected at one metre below the ground level.

Figure 6. Sub-profile image from seismic refraction and SPT N-Value from borehole 1 and 2 at (a) Section 44 and (b) Section 43.7, FT005.

Figure 7. Borehole soil strata for BH1 and BH2.

Figure 8. Resistivity images produce by using gradient protocol along 100m length at (a) Section 43.7 and (b) Section 44, FT005.

Figure 9. Resistivity result at Line R6a at Section 43.7, FT005 from Pontian to Johor Bahru.

Figure 9 shows the additional resistivity testing with 1-meter spacing was conducted at Section 44 to analyse the shallow sub-profile and to get the good resolution of image 1m below the road surface instead of using 2.5m spacing. There was a high possibility of very soft soil up to 7m below the pavement layer. There was identified the potential zone of saturated water due to the low result of resistivity with saturated water.

4.4 Condition of concrete slab.

Based on coring and DCP (Table 3), the concrete slabs were in poor condition. The position of the concrete slab at three points of trenches (trial pit) was detected at difference level from road level. GPR is another geophysical survey test that has been adopted in this study to investigate the existing condition of in situ concrete slab. The measurement of GPR lines (G1, G2, G3 and G4) were conducted as grid line to represent slice image. The result of GPR in Figure 10 and 11 were analysed and classified based on amplitude value stated in Table 6. High amplitude reflection zone represents in red colour shows the position of concrete slab. Refer to Figure 10 and 11, most red amplitude identified at depth 0.00-0.25m and 0.25-0.50m. Because of inconsistency red colour zone identified between 0.00-0.50m below the road surface, there was a possibility that the concrete slab has been moved either vertically (settlement) or horizontally. The present of thick layer of soft soils underneath the pavement layer was the possibility factor that cause a movement and settlement of concrete slab.

Figure 10. Image analysis from GPR at each layer of depth at Section 43.7, FT005 - (a) Line G3 from Johor Bahru and (b) Line G4 from Pontian/ Malacca.

Figure 11. Image analysis produced from GPR at each layer of depth at Section 44, FT005 – (a) Line G1 from Johor Bahru and (b) Line G2 from Pontian/ Malacca.

Table 6. The classification of concrete slab and soil based on amplitude value of GPR.

Normalized Amplitude value	Legends	Interpretations
<4000		Low reflection amplitude (Zone of soil with saturated water)
>4000		High reflection amplitude (Zone of unsaturated water)

5. Conclusion

Based on investigation that has been conducted, the tension crack and settlement occurred along Section 43-44, FT005 were due to the causes listed below:

- Settlement process of soft ground layer. Based on seismic, ERT and borehole/ SPT show the correlation. The thick layer of very soft clay was identified about 7m below the subgrade layer. From the geological map, this section located at quaternary sediment, which comprises alluvial deposits and organic or peat soils. However, from the results of borehole, the organic content was less than 20%;
- Increase of surcharge loading due to the repeated process of resurfacing of pavement. The thickness of asphalt layer identified increase up to 1m. Increase of static loading (asphalt layer) and dynamic loading (heavy vehicles) made the settlement become worst;
- Instability factors at embankment road slope can be one of the problems which can accelerate the process of settlement at selected section.; and
- Deviation of concrete slab from the original position clearly shown from the result of GPR. The deviation of concrete slab cause differential settlement along the route. Different method of construction at widening section was another factor of differential settlement occurred at the edge of concrete slab.

As conclusion, the results of boreholes were consistent with the soil profiles analysed by geophysical surveys (Seismic and Resistivity). The geophysical survey is an additional equipment that can give a good indicator before carrying any destructive testing such as borehole. The geophysical survey provides comprehensive data of subsurface characteristics. The right selection of testing and method can produce the correct and best data interpretation. Therefore, the road needs to redesign to fit the current condition and the development of the area.

6. References

- [1] Philip Kearey, Michael Brooks and Ian Hill 2002 *An Introduction to Geophysical Exploration* Blackwell Science Ltd. p 14
- [2] Sufiyanussuari et. al 2021 Forensic Study on Federal Road Pavement Failures and Semerah, Batu Pahat *J. Sustainable Underground Exploration* **Vol.1** p 10-19
- [3] Samsudin and Ahmad Nizam, 2002 A Meaningful correlation between shallow seismic refraction borehole data in site investigation work. *Geological Society of Malaysia Annual Geological Conference* p. 351-358
- [4] Keller, G.V. and Frischknecht, F.C. 1996 *Electrical Method In Geophysics Prospecting* Pergamon Press, Inc. Oxford p 517
- [5] Selia Selenggara Selatan Sdn. Bhd. 2019 *Report of Structural Condition Assessment* p 1-26

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